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Morphing wingtip structure based on active inflatable honeycomb and shape memory polymer composite skin: a conceptual work

Jian Sun, HIT China

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Introduction

- Morphing wing technologies for aircraft designs are receiving significant attention due to their potential benefits to extend the flight envelope of classical fixed-wing aircraft . **A morphing wingtip technology** could bring several improvements on the overall performance of an airplane:
 - The lift to drag ratio during climb could be improved
 - Vertex-induced drag during high-speed flight could be reduced
 - The maneuverability could also be improved
 - Fuel consumption could be adaptively reduced

Introduction

- Shape Memory Polymers (SMP) are considered a variable stiffness material controlled by temperature. The SMP skins alter shape, with their microstructure in rubbery state at low stiffness, and can withstand aerodynamic loads in the glassy state with high stiffness. SMP skins have been already evaluated for morphing chord wings, folding, deployable, and variable camber wings.

Shape memory effect (Lan *et al.*, 2009)

Morphing wingtip Concept

- The wingtip rests in a deployed state with a larger physical aspect ratio wing (a) during take-off and climb phases. The lift/drag ratio can be improved for shorter takeoff distances

Morphing wingtip Concept

- When the configuration of the wingtip needs to be changed (i.e., flap-up to reduce the induced drag or modify the roll rate) the SMPC skin should be heated to decrease its stiffness. No input pressure to the tubes is applied, but the wingtip flaps up under the pressure differential between the upper and lower surface of the wing. After reaching the designed final position, the SMPC skin is cooled down to become stiff to form a stable winglet configuration

Morphing wingtip Concept

- The wingtip can again deploy based on the operational flight requirements, and in that case the tubes are inflated after the SMPC skin has been heated up. With a subsequent cooling of the skin temperature, the deploy wingtip configuration is fixed

Modelling

Assumptions:

1. The two butterfly cellular structures and the internal tubes are equal and symmetric with respect to interface line between the two tubes.
2. The line connecting the centres of the two arcs intersects the two straight cell walls at point O . The section of a tube is symmetric with respect to this line.
3. There is no sliding between the tubes and the honeycomb walls, i.e. the parameter ' h ' in Figure 2 is a constant

Modelling

Allowable design envelopes for a_1 and a_2

Curves of α and β versus ϑ

Modelling

$$F_1 = (F_{r1} - F_{r0}) = \frac{EI}{\cos\left(\frac{\theta}{4}\right)} \left(\frac{1}{\left(r_1 - \frac{t}{2}\right)^2} - \frac{1}{\left(R_0 - \frac{t}{2}\right)^2} \right)$$

$$F_2 = \frac{EI}{\cos\left(\frac{\theta}{4}\right)} \left(\frac{1}{\left(r_2 - \frac{t}{2}\right)^2} - \frac{1}{\left(R_0 - \frac{t}{2}\right)^2} \right)$$

Modelling

Simulacra of the morphing of the wingtip configuration without shape memory polymer skin and with black inflatable tubes at different input pressures

Modelling

Wingtip angle versus input pressure from experiments and model results

Theoretical wingtip angle versus the input pressure for different external loading values

Modelling

Deployment of the wingtip demonstrator with the SMPC skin

Morphing skin stiffening using PMFs

Contour deformations plots for the SMPC skin in glass state (left) with the PMFs and in rubber state with the PMFs (right)

Testing apparatus to verify the load bearing capacity of the SMPCs with and without pneumatic muscle fibers

Morphing skin stiffening using PMFs

SMPC maximum displacements with and without PMF stringers at different input pressures

Maximum displacement comparison between simulations and experiment for SMP skin with the PMFs

Conclusions

- This work has described the concept of a morphing wingtip based on an active deployable honeycomb pneumatics actuation and a shape memory polymer/carbon skin.
- The geometrical configuration and the mechanical performance of the active honeycomb under compression was modelled.
- The input pressure/wingtip angle relationship for the morphing wingtip system was also verified.
- A simulacra of morphing wingtip was fabricated, which has shown the feasibility of this concept for possible morphing wingtip configurations for further application.
- Pneumatic fiber muscles have been developed as adaptive stiffeners to adjust the bending and membrane stiffness of the shape memory polymer skin during deployment.
- The operational effectiveness of the stiffened SMPC plate was verified by experimental tests produced in an ad-hoc rig, and Finite Element models that provided a good agreement with the experimental trends measured.
- The concept described in this paper may be further evaluated for the use of small UAVs (less than 800 kg), or for other adaptive structures designs in which shape memory polymers could find their use.